

A FRAMEWORK FOR THE APPLICATION OF ROBUST DESIGN METHODS AND TOOLS

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Introduction and Objective

Robust Design

- Design to achieve consistent functional performance in spite of variation
- Minimize variation of functional performance regardless of manufacturing, assembly and load variations, variation due to ambient conditions and variation over time
- Knowledge in industry is poor [1], [2], [3]
- Application of RD tools in industry often incorrect [1], [2], [3]
- No single framework or process for application of RD tools in industry [4]

Previous Studies

- Focused on attributes, philosophies, practices of RD
- Limitations in increasing the understanding of the tools

The aim of the framework is to increase the understanding and provide support for the application of RD methods.

A Framework for the Application of RD Methods and Tools

Methodology

- List of methods and tools associated with RD in literature has been extracted from previous reviews and classifications
- Augmented with tools from authors' experiences
- Find main premise of methods and tools
- Create framework by means of KJ-Analysis and Faceted Classification

Facets of the Classification

Robust Design Guidance and Principles

Methods and tools support the designer from the concept level to the final product in designing in robustness. Design rules and proposals from experiences in mechanical design are utilized to decrease the sensitivity to variation.

Robustness Evaluation

Methods and tools give relative or absolute (metric) information about how sensitive to variation a design is. Per se these tools do not improve the robustness of a product but give an important input for comparisons of design solutions or even estimated yield rates and the prediction of reliability as a support in the decision making process.

Robustness Optimization

Methods and tools support the designer in exploring the design space and optimizing the design on the basis of the gained information.

Robustness Visualization

Robustness Visualization refers to tools, for instance, figures, diagrams or matrices that help to increase the awareness of robustness to variation without improving or quantifying the robustness of the design.

		Robust Design Guidance and Principles	Robust Design Evaluation	Robustness Optimization	Robustness Visualization
1	Axiomatic Design	X			
2	Design Clarity	X	X*		
3	Design Matrix		X		
4	Design Principles	X			
5	DoE			X	
6	Kinematic Design	X	X*		
7	Locating Scheme	X			
8	Monte-Carlo-Analysis		X		
9	P-Diagram				X
10	Taguchi Method		X	X	
11	Physical Decomposition of Functions	X			
12	Ishikava / Fishbone Diagram				X
13	Quality Loss Functions				X
14	QFD / House of Quality				X
15	Sensitivity Studies		X	X	
16	Transfer Functions		X*	X	
17	Tolerance Management	X	X	X	
18	VMEA		X		
19	Response Surface Methodology		X	X	

X* Robust Evaluation in early design stage

Bibliography

- [1] Araujo C.S., Benedetto-Neto H., Campello A.C., Segre F.M., Wright I.C., 1996. The utilization of product development methods: A survey of UK industry. *Journal of Engineering Design*, Vol. 7, pp 265-277.
 [2] Gremyr I., Arvidsson M., Johansson P., 2003. Robust Design Methodology: Status in the Swedish Manufacturing Industry. *Quality and Reliability Engineering International*, Vol. 19, pp. 285-293
 [3] Thornton A. C., Donnelly S., Ertan B., 2000. More than just Robust Design: Why product development organizations still contend with variation and its impact on quality. *Research in Engineering Design*, Vol. 12, pp. 127-143.
 [4] Krogstie, L., Ebro, M., Howard, T.J., 2014. How to implement and apply robust design: insights from industrial practice. *Total Quality Management & Business Excellence* (Print), DOI: 10.1080/14783363.2014.934520

Example Case – Design of DVD Player Sled

Design of a DVD player sled with following main functional requirements

1. Sled driving force $< F_{Motor, max}$
2. Laser position accuracy $< \Delta r_{track}$

Robust Design Guidance and Principles

Robustness Evaluation

Derive Transfer function:
Sled driving force

$$F_{sled} = m \cdot a + F_{friction} + F_{Deformation}$$

Transfer Function for the dependence of the driving force to the parallelism of the rails for both design concepts

Robustness Optimization

Taguchi Method for Concept B:

- Parameter Design
 - DoE / Orthogonal arrays (or Transfer Functions)
 - Selection of DPs (a-m) considering constraints (size of DVD, structural integrity, manufacturability, etc.) for smallest variation of the functional performance
→ maximize SN-Ratio (variation = noise)
- Tolerance Design

Example:
angular displacement of laser

Laser displacements due to tilting:
Function of (a, c, e, f, h, g, k) with different single sensitivities
→ Optimal nominal values and tolerances to be assigned

Robustness Visualization

Increasing the awareness of sensitivity to variation and visualization of important factors to be considered in the design process:

Conclusions

- Framework clarifies the underlying premises of the methods and tools related to RD and supports the application
- Lack of options for Robustness Evaluation in early design
- Classification can help to identify overlaps as well as differences between methods and finally lead to successful integrations and combinations of tools.